

DELIVERABLE

Project Number: 964591

Project Acronym: SMART-electron

Project Title: Ultrafast All-Optical Spatio-Temporal
Electron Modulators: Opening New Frontiers In Electron Microscopy

Funding Scheme: H2020-FETOPEN-2018-2020

Number of Work Package	WP6
Number of Deliverable	D6.5
Title of Deliverable	Graphic assets for Dissemination and Communication activities (first release)
Lead Beneficiary	QED
Due Date	M10

Start Date of Project: 01/05/2021

Duration: 48 months

Graphic assets for Dissemination and Communication activities (first release)

D6.5

Version 1.0

Authors:

Luca M.C. Giberti (QED)
Raffaella Santucci (QED)

Reviewers:

Giovanni Maria Vanacore (UNIMIB)

Project funded by the European Commission within the FET OPEN Programme		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	X
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Revision History

Revision	Authors	Organisation	Description
0.1	Raffaella Santucci	QED	First draft
0.2	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti Raffaella Santucci	QED QED	First complete version
0.3	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti Raffaella Santucci	QED QED	Second complete version - overall cleanup and insertion of text+images
0.4	Raffaella Santucci	QED	Added jpgs of designs, intro and conclusions
0.5	Giovanni Maria Vanacore	UNIMIB	Review and comments, minor changes
0.6	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti Raffaella Santucci	QED QED	Feedback integrated, overall revision, added links and further explanations/thoughts
0.7	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti Raffaella Santucci Giovanni Maria Vanacore	QED QED UNIMIB	Overall revision
1.0	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti	QED	Revised final version incorporating reviewers' suggestions and minor amendments

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Disclaimer

The sole responsibility for the content of this deliverable lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the REA nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1 INTRODUCTION - WHO WILL BE USING THESE DESIGNS AND THIS DELIVERABLE?	6
2 DESIGN PHILOSOPHY	7
3 LIST OF THE GRAPHIC ASSETS THAT WERE PRODUCED	7
3.1 The Actual Design Process	8
3.2 Copywriting	12
4 LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS	13
5 CONCLUSIONS	22
ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS	23
Short Name Of Participants	23
List Of Abbreviations	23

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a short overview of the production of all print and presentation materials that will be used for the communication and dissemination of SMART-electron. All future printed materials for SMART-electron will be based on the designs and templates described in this document. Printed materials play a key role in dissemination and communication, as the first impression one gets of the project, which cannot be undone, is imparted by them.

This document comprises four chapters.

Chapter 1 is a short introduction.

Chapter 2 provides a brief overview of the philosophy behind the design of the dissemination materials.

Chapter 3 provides a list of the designs that were produced and details how the design and copywriting process unfolded.

Chapter 4 provides low-resolution copies of the above designs.

Chapter 4 sums up the conclusions and take-home messages that were gleaned through this work.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHO WILL BE USING THESE DESIGNS AND THIS DELIVERABLE?

Within SMART-electron the dissemination and communication materials are tools that will be used by:

- All partners
- All WP leaders
- Particularly by the staff responsible for each institution's communication activities.

In addition, as this is a public document and is available on the project's website, it will be accessible by external parties interested in disseminating and communicating SMART-electron.

This deliverable will be updated periodically at a later phase of the project according to the project's needs.

2 DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

The design of the printed materials was based on two simple but effective requirements: starting from the existing project logo, and tweaking the project website if necessary, we aimed to attain a graphic identity that is at the same time distinctive and classic. Achieving both a degree of timelessness and a striking design that 'speaks to everyone' has in turn two significant consequences. The branding guidelines as given in D6.3 were also drafted with this two-fold goal in mind.

A timeless and classic look means that the design is conceived to 'age well'.

On the other hand, a strong graphic statement that is simple, easy to identify, and based on universal proportions (such as for instance certain mathematical ratios) allows the use of the same design/theme for both dissemination and communication. This strong visual identity was consistently 'declined' in the various print designs, as detailed in the next chapter.

Both considerations translate into cost and labour savings for the project, especially with a view to its future upkeep/sustainability.

Another cost-saving consideration was the idea of designing templates for brochures and posters that the partners will be able to easily fill in and print locally as the need arises (see below).

3 LIST OF THE GRAPHIC ASSETS THAT WERE PRODUCED

In terms of printed materials for dissemination and communication, the needs of such an ambitious project as SMART-electron are many. Broadly speaking, some printed assets are meant to be general-purpose, i.e. deployable anywhere without any changes, whilst others are event-specific, i.e. tailored to each specific SMART-electron International Conference or event. Based on the project schedule as well as on an evaluation of the overall progress so far (and in particular on D6.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan), the following assets were thus identified and then designed:

1. foldable two-sided general-purpose square Project brochure;
2. template for conference-specific A2 Project poster;
3. general-purpose 80x200 Project vinyl banner;
4. template for the A4 Project conference programmes;
5. general-purpose SMART-electron-branded tote bag;
6. template for SMART-electron slides
7. favicons and social media icons/banners
8. graphic design guidelines.

1) General-purpose two-fold square brochure, to be deployed at various events as a general presentation of the project. The choice of a square format is due to reasons of compatibility with the square aspect ratio favoured for online assets (Instagram, browser favicons, shortcut icons on mobiles, etc.).

2) Template for event-specific vertical A2 poster, printable as A3 if necessary. The choice of a standard ISO 216 / DIN format instead of more 'fashionable' ones translates into savings for the project and in no way diminishes the impact of the design. A2 was chosen as the largest possible format that can be hung without too much trouble in pinboards and public spaces – since, trivially, a larger format guarantees

greater visibility. The design is compatible with printing in A3, which is significantly cheaper for small runs of digital prints.

3) General-purpose 80x200 standalone vinyl banner, to advertise and signal events taking place in a specific venue, such as conferences, seminars, lectures, press conferences, etc. The choice of PVC as the printing material makes the roll-up banner suitable for outdoor use as well.

4) Template for the event-specific A4 conference programmes, which provides readers with the schedule for all the topics of all the talks and all the posters presented at the conference, as well as a list of all participants. It is also meant as a memento of the conference for all participants.

5) General-purpose SMART-electron-branded tote bag, to be given to all conference participants as well as to guests.

6) Template for SMART-electron slide presentations. To be used by all partners when presenting on behalf of SMART-electron. A set of coherent graphic rules is given in the template.

7) Browser favicons and social media icons & banners were derived from the logo and optimised according to the various social media guidelines.

8) Graphic design guidelines for the correct deployment of graphic assets (including the Logo) were produced in the form of a PDF booklet, which was distributed to partners.

Insofar as possible, SMART-electron designs will be printed locally by partners, close to where they are meant to be deployed, in order to save on expenses and environmental impact. The designs are sent to partners with specific instructions as to the type of printing process, paper, and finish to be adopted, so as to ensure a consistently high standard of quality.

All the designs were optimised for offset printing but can be output as high-quality laser or inkjet prints if necessary.

3.1 THE ACTUAL DESIGN PROCESS

Work on the designs for SMART-electron's printed materials was conceived from the outset to evolve based on the graphic design done previously for the project: from the outset, we sought to expand as a coherent whole the system of typesetting and design rules underlying the project's graphic identity. Hence, starting from the existing logo and website (described in D6.1 Project Logo and Webpage), two different concepts were developed and explored.

The first one consists of evoking photons and electrons through the stylisation and extensive repetition of the S and the E in the project logo. The curved elements of the S and the straight elements of the E can in fact be thought of as corresponding to the photon and electron lines in Feynman diagrams. This dichotomy is appropriate for SE, which is all about shaping electron matter waves by using photons. At the same time, the curved and the straight element can be viewed as symbolic of the wave/particle duality which is one of the defining features of Quantum Mechanics.

The second concept revolves around the idea of the correspondence between theory and experiment. The inspiration for this was a figure in the 2018 Nature Communications paper on attosecond control of free electrons by Vanacore et al¹.

The starting point for the 'theory vs. experiment' concept for the graphic assets:
 the plots in <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-018-05021-x.pdf>

In the figure, the theoretical prediction for the light field amplitude vs. electron energy loss plot for the light-electron interaction is compared with the plot obtained through measurement. Since the interplay between theory/simulation and experiment is at the very heart of physics, we thought of applying an analogous graphic stylisation to the SMART-electron logotype, whereby the smooth predictions of theory are symbolised by the anti-aliased, vector-graphics version of the SMART-electron logotype, whereas the pixelated and noisy outcome of experiment is represented by the same logotype with added spatial distortion and rasterised with large pixels.

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-018-05021-x.pdf>

Early sketches for the poster (L) and the vinyl banner (R) based on the 'theory vs. experiment' concept

The same dichotomy was exploited for the inner fold of the brochure, where the two plots from the above paper mirror one another, with the symmetry about the vertical axis broken by the theory-vs-experiment discrepancy.

As to the use of colour, we followed our custom of relying on strong contrasts and simple colour schemes. In particular, we sought to build on the palette we chose for the website - by adopting the lime yellow we used for the webpages and logo, as well as its complementary colour for selected elements, such as the inner fold of the brochure:

Two early versions of the inner fold of the brochure based on the 'theory vs. experiment' concept and using the colour complement to the lime green of the Logo

In terms of paper formats, for speed of print and best value for money, we adopted standard DIN formats whenever possible - for example for the A2 poster for events. The brochure and the vinyl banner are an exception to our self-imposed "DIN-only" rule: we opted for a square brochure with a single inner fold due to reasons of compatibility with the square aspect ratio used in Instagram, as well as for browser favicons and link icons on mobile platforms. Having a unified design for all these assets -Instagram posts, favicons, mobile icons- makes a lot of sense since the SMART-electron presence across platforms is more immediately recognisable this way. The vinyl banner has a custom aspect ratio due to the brand-specific aspect ratio of the available blanks on which it is printed.

In the end, the first 'wave vs. particle' concept was deemed more impactful and won over the second one, which only survives in the inner fold of the brochure. Having settled on the main concept and proportions, special care was taken in considering the interplay of the designs with the type of paper and of printing method intended for each of the assets/formats. Then we proceeded to consistently 'decline' the leitmotiv in the various designs, which are shown in the next chapter. Throughout the design phase, all the guidelines regarding the use of the various official logos were observed.

3.2 COPYWRITING

Similar considerations of simplicity and efficacy were adopted for the copywriting. The latter, insofar as possible, eschewed lingo in favour of clear and simple explanations, understandable by the general public, but also providing meaningful information for specialists. The text can be read from the second figure in the next chapter.

4 LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS

The SMART-electron two-fold brochure

The SMART-electron vertical A2 poster, which is also the template for event-specific posters

The SMART-electron vinyl banner

The SMART-electron vinyl banner

*The SMART-electron template for conference programmes
(outer cover)*

The SMART-electron tote bags

**linesWork Package 1:
 Modelling, design and
 characterization of a
 Photonic free- Electron
 Modulator (PELM)**

**Kick-off Meeting
 May 4th 2021**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964591

Schedule

Gantt chart

Please illustrate dependencies among tasks and within WPs

Please indicate start and end month of the WP and of its related tasks

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, lacus nulla ac netus nibh aliquet, porttitor ligula justo libero vivamus porttitor dolor, conubia mollit. Sapien nam suspendisse, tincidunt eget ante tincidunt, eros in auctor fringilla praesent at diam. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, lacus nulla ac netus nibh aliquet.

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, lacus nulla ac netus nibh aliquet, porttitor ligula justo libero vivamus porttitor dolor, conubia mollit. Sapien nam suspendisse, tincidunt eget ante tincidunt, eros in auctor fringilla praesent at diam. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, lacus nulla ac netus nibh aliquet.

Quantized electron light interaction

The vision behind the SMART electron project relies on a light mediated coherent modulation of the longitudinal and transverse phase of an electron wave function exploiting the strong interaction between free electrons and optical fields in illuminated nanostructures

$$(1+x)^n = 1 + \frac{nx}{1} + \frac{n(n-1)x^2}{2!} + \dots + x^n$$

$$(1+x)^n = 1 + \frac{nx}{1!} + \frac{n(n-1)x^2}{2!} + \dots + x^n$$

Static shaping of electron beams

a incident beam, spiral phase plate, vortex beam

b incident beam, ℓ_n -fork hologram, diffracted vortex beams ($\ell = -\ell_0, \ell = 0, \ell = \ell_0$)

c incident beam, magnetic monopole, vortex beam ($\ell = \ell_0$)

Templates for SMART-electron slides

SMART-electron browser favicon (L) and Facebook/Whatsapp group icon (R)

SMART-electron Springboard icon next to those of the [Q-SORT](#) and [MINEON](#) EC projects

SMART-electron Facebook banners

Select pages from the SMART-electron graphic design guidelines booklet

5 CONCLUSIONS

We think the results show the benefit of involving a professional media production company with the right profile in the design and copywriting process.

Suitable 'buffer time' needs to be scheduled between completion of the designs to the coordinator's and designers' satisfaction, and their final delivery. This is in order to take into account possible changes at the request of partners or of those institutions whose logo is included in the design. The number and duration of these 'refinement iterations' can be assumed to grow with a power law with the number of partners involved.

Further suitable buffer time should be factored in for checking printed samples ahead of each print run: the correct rendition of text, logos, and graphics/colours should be checked, as well as the quality of the folding in the case of the brochures.

The Consortium now has general-purpose brochures, posters, stand-alone banners, and tote bags ready for any event.

Partners now have all the templates at their disposal, so that they can start planning the printing of their own posters and brochures.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
1 UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO-BICOCCA	ITALY	UNIMIB
2 ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE EPFL	SWITZERLAND	EPFL
3 FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE CIENCIES FOTONIQUES	SPAIN	ICFO
4 TECHNION - ISRAEL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	ISRAEL	TECHNION
5 CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	ITALY	CNR
6 HOLOEYE PHOTONICS AG	GERMANY	HOLOEYE
7 QED FILM & STAGE PRODUCTIONS LTD	UK	QED

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL